

Schnyder, C. & Hollier, J. (2022) MINERALS AND ROCKS COLLECTIONS BY ALBERT BRUN (1857-1939), PHARMACIST AND VOLCANOLOGIST IN GENEVA, Earth Sciences History.

Supplementary material 1: Albert Brun in Swiss geoscience collections

This inventory lists all the known Brun samples in the holdings of Swiss museums. The names of the samples are those on the original labels, adapted according to their probable petrographic nature based on maps and subsequent geological surveys. A precise determination and classification would require the examination of thin sections and geochemical analyses, especially for volcanic rocks. Provenances and country names have been simplified and updated. The MHNG samples ranging from Br001 to Br311 already had a provisional numbering before their definitive integration into the collections of the museum.

Collections of the Natural History Museum of Geneva (MHNG)

Basalt	Br 001	Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Andesite	Br 002	Semeru, Java, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 003	Haleakala, Hawaii, USA
Basalt	Br 004	Maui, Hawaii, USA
Andesite	Br 005	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 006	San Gaetano, Pantelleria, Italy
Basalt	Br 007	Hilo, Hawaii, USA
Basalt	Br 008	Keana Kakoi, Hawaii, USA
Basalt	Br 009	Haleakala, Maui, Hawaii, USA
Basalt	Br 010	Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Granite + divers	Br 011	Forno, Grisons, Switzerland
Basalt	Br 012	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Basalt	Br 013	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Basalt	Br 014	Agde, Ft. St.Thybery, Hérault, France
Granite	Br 015	Forno, Grisons, Switzerland
Basalt + tephra	Br 016	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Basalt	Br 017	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Xenolithe	Br 018	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Basalt	Br 019	Agde, Ft. St Thybéry, Hérault, France
Chrysotile	Br 020	Canciono
Basalt	Br 021	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Basalt	Br 022	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Basalt	Br 023	Olot, Gerona, Catalogne, Spain
Skarn	Br 024	Forno, Maloja, Grisons, Switzerland
Lepidolite	Br 025	Forno, Grisons, Switzerland
Obsidian	Br 026	Cluj-Napoca, Rumania (Kolozsodr, Hungary)
Marcassite	Br 027	Unknown locality
Andesite?	Br 028	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain

Tuf	Br 029	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Andesite	Br 030	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte?	Br 031	Pico de Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Phonolite	Br 032	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Diorite?	Br 033	Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Ponce	Br 034	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 035	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 036	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 037	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 038	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 039	Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 040	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 041	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 042	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 043	Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 044	Ile de la Réunion, France
Basalt	Br 045	Dasar, Java, Indonesia
Fulgurite ?	Br 046	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Dacite + Andesite	Br 047	Kvabatan, Java, Indonesia
Tuf	Br 048	Unknown locality
Basalt	Br 049	Dasar, Java, Indonesia
Brèche	Br 050	Kongkodjadjan, Java, Indonesia
Andesite	Br 051	Île de Kabatan, Java, Indonesia
Pumice	Br 052	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Tephra	Br 053	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Lapilli	Br 054	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 055	Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Andesite?	Br 056	Crater Kawah(?), Java, Indonesia
Andesite	Br 057	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Divers	Br 058	Padang, Sumatra, Indonesia
Ponce	Br 059	Dasav, Java, Indonesia
Andesite	Br 060	Djakarta, Java, Indonesia
Téphrite?	Br 061	Tangkuban Perahu, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 062	Hilo, Hawaii, USA
Dacite	Br 063	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 064	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 065	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 066	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece

Dacite?	Br 067	Phira, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 068	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Ponce	Br 069	Santorini, Greece
Dacite?	Br 070	Pyrgos, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 071	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 072	Santorini, Greece
Dacite ?	Br 073	Pyrgos, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 074	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite?	Br 075	Thira, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 076	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 077	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 078	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 079	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 080	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 081	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite?	Br 082	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 083	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 084	Nea Kameni, Santorini, Greece
Asbestos	Br 085	Alpe Quadrata, Grisons, Switzerland
Asbestos	Br 086	Alpe Quadrata, Grisons, Switzerland
Orthose	Br 087	Unknown locality
Obsidian	Br 088	Cabo de Gata, Spain
Pegmatite	Br 089	Osogna, Tessin, Switzerland
Serpentinite	Br 090	Diatte de Cauciano?, Poschiavo, Grisons, Switzerland
Tephra	Br 091	Semeru, Java, Indonesia
Dacite	Br 092	Santorini, Greece
Pyroxénite?	Br 093	Geisspfad, Binntal, Valais, Switzerland
Grès	Br 094	Svalbard, Norway
Basalt	Br 095	Lanzarote, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 096	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Dacite? + Obsidian	Br 097	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Opale?	Br 098	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Soufre	Br 099	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Dacite? (Andesite?)	Br 100	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 101	Halemaumau, Hawaii, USA
Dacite?	Br 102	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 103	Ile de Perim, Yemen
Basalt	Br 104	Esja, Reykjavik, Iceland

Ponce	Br 105	Askja, Iceland
Ponce	Br 106	Askja, Iceland
Echantillons divers	Br 107	Askja, Iceland
Ponce	Br 108	Askja, Iceland
Lapilli	Br 109	Reykjavik, Iceland
Lapilli	Br 110	Laki, Iceland
Tephra	Br 111	Krisuvik, Iceland
Basalt?	Br 112	Kollotadyngja, Iceland
Echantillons divers	Br 113	Krisuvik, Iceland
Trachyte phonolitique	Br 114	Cape Barne, Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Basalt	Br 115	Cape Barne, Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Limonite	Br 116	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Marbre	Br 117	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Trachyte phonolitique	Br 118	Mt Erebus, Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Basalt	Br 119	Cape Royds, Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Trachyte phonolitique	Br 120	Cape Royds, Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
lave poreuse basique	Br 121	Mc Murdo, Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Trachyte phonolitique	Br 122	Cap Royds, Ross Sound, Ross Sound, Antarctica
Téphrite	Br 123	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Téphrite	Br 124	Unknown locality
Lapilli	Br 125	Vesuve, Campania, Italy
Produits fumerolliens	Br 126	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Obsidian	Br 137	Cabo de Gata, Almeria, Andalousie, Spain
Basalt?	Br 128	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Tephra	Br 129	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Tephra	Br 130	Vesuvius, Amalfi, Italy (?)
Produits fumerolliens	Br 131	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Produits fumerolliens	Br 132	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Obsidian	Br 133	Viterbo, Rome, Latium, Italy
Scoria	Br 134	Semeru, Java, Indonesia
Obsidian	Br 127	Akk Dagh, Sivas, Turkey
Obsidian	Br 135	Cabo de Gata, Almeria, Andalousie, Spain
Obsidian	Br 136	Cabo de Gata, Almeria, Andalousie, Spain
Sulphur	Br 138	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Asbestos	Br 139	Val Madra, Tessin, Switzerland
Granite	Br 140	Resega Valley near Pontresina, Tessin (Val Roseg, Pontresina, Grisons ?)
Pegmatite	Br 141	Osogna, Riviera, Tessin, Switzerland
Pegmatite	Br 142	Vadrec del Forno, Val Bregaglia, Grisons, Switzerland

Talc	Br 143	Poschiavo, Grisons, Switzerland
Basalt	Br 144	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 145	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Lapillis	Br 146	Chinyero, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte Andesite	Br 147	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Scoria	Br 148	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Sand	Br 149	Lanzarote, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 150	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 151	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 152	Guimar, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Granulite	Br 153	Magdalena Bay, Svalbard, Norway
Gypse	Br 154	Green Harbour, Svalbard, Norway
Quartz + talc	Br 155	Bellsund, Svalbard, Norway
Charbon	Br 156	Green Harbour, Svalbard, Norway
Quartzite (grès compact?)	Br 157	Green Harbour, Svalbard, Norway
Granulite	Br 159	Magdalena Bay, Svalbard, Norway
Quartzite, sandstone, silex	Br 158	Green Harbour, Svalbard, Norway
Aplite diabasique	Br 160	Svalbard, Norway
Aplite diabasique	Br 161	Svalbard, Norway
Basalt	Br 162	Svalbard, Norway
Sandstone	Br 163	Svalbard, Norway
Asbestos	Br 164	Svalbard, Norway
péridotite?	Br 165	Bellsund, Svalbard, Norway
gabbro	Br 166	Svalbard, Norway
sidérite ?	Br 167	Svalbard, Norway
Basalt	Br 168	Guimar, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 169	Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 170	Mozaga, Lanzarote, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 172	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt (filon)	Br 173	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 174	Guimar, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Téphrite	Br 175	Pedro Gil, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte et Téphrite	Br 176	Pedro Gil, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt (fulgurite ?)	Br 177	Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Lapillis	Br 178	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 179	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte	Br 180	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 181	Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain

Trachyte	Br 182	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 183	Guimar, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 184	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Obsidian	Br 185	Plomb du Cantal, Cantal, Auvergne Rhône-Alpes, France
Phonolite	Br 186	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Basalt	Br 187	Banks Peninsula, Niue, South Island, Nouvelle-Zélande
Basalt	Br 188	Castlerock of Edimburgh, Ecosse, Royaume-Uni
Basalt	Br 189	Vermicino, Frascati, Rome, Latium, Italy
Phonolite? Basalt?	Br 189	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Basalt	Br 190	Vesuvius, Italy
Calcsilicate	Br 191	Vesuvius, Italy
Basalt	Br 192	Vesuvius, Italy
Basalt	Br 193	Acquant (?), Rome, Italy
Phonolite	Br 194	Vesuvius, Italy
Basalt	Br 195	Vesuvius, Italy
Téphrite	Br 196	Vesuvius, Italy
Basalt	Br 197	Vesuvius, Italy
Téphrite	Br 198	Vesuvius, Italy
Basalt	Br 199	Mt Erebus, Mc Murdo Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Pumices	Br 200	Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Tephra	Br 201	Etna, Sicile, Italy
Andesite	Br 202	Spagnuolo, Etna, Sicile, Italy
Basalt	Br 203	Moio, Etna, Italy
Basalt	Br 204	Cape Barne, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Bombes	Br 205	Spagnuolo, Etna, Italy
Trachyte	Br 206	Etna, Sicile, Italy
Basalt	Br 207	Catania, Sicile, Italy
Basalt	Br 208	Arizona, USA
Basalt	Br 209	« Old Faithful », Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Various rocks	Br 210	Unknown locality
Augite	Br 211	St Paul Island, Alaska, USA
Pumices	Br 212	Cabo de Gata, Almeria, Andalousia, Spain
Olivine	Br 213	TeanaKakoi, Hawaii, USA
Pumices	Br 214	Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Heated rock	Br 215	Cabo de Gata, Almeria, Spain
Sand	Br 216	India
Sand	Br 217	Enoshima, Kanagawa, Japan
Heated rock	Br 218	Cabo de Gata, Almeria, Andalousia, Spain

Basalt	Br 219	Espaly, Haute Loire, Auvergne Rhône-Alpes, France
Basalt	Br 220	Kilauea, Hawaii, USA
Basalt	Br 221	Manzat, Puy-de-Dôme, Auvergne Rhône-Alpes, France
Augite	Br 222	St Paul, Alaska, USA
Basalt	Br 223	Etna, Sicile, Italy
Basalt	Br 224	Ross Sound, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Phonolite	Br 225	Mt Erebus, Sud Victorialand, Antarctica
Dacite	Br 226	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 227	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 228	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 229	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 230	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 231	Santorini, Greece
dacite	Br 232	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 233	Georgios, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 234	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 235	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 236	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 237	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 238	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 239	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 240	Santorini, Greece
Basalt	Br 241	Yaza, Lanzarote, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 242	Timanfaya, Lanzarote, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 243	Timanfaya, Lanzarote, Canaries, Spain
Bombes	Br 244	Timanfaya, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 245	Arrecife, Lanzarote, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 246	Laus de Azurre and the caldeira Fencaliente, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Tephra	Br 456	Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 248	El Portillo, La Orotava, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 249	Montana Blanca, Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 250	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 251	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Trachyte Andesite	Br 252	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt and pumice	Br 253	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 254	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 255	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 256	Java, Indonesia

Basaltic Limburgite	Br 257	Santa Cruz, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 258	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Andesite	Br 259	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Andesite	Br 260	Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 261	Montana Blanca, Alta Vista, Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt ?	Br 262	Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt?	Br 263	Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt	Br 264	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Echantillon refondu	Br 265	Puerto Viejo, Chahorra, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Phonolite?	Br 266	La Rambletta, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Andesite	Br 267	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Phonolite?	Br 268	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 269	Montana Blanca, Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Phonolite?	Br 270	Pico de Teide, Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Obsidian	Br 271	Tenerife, Canaries, Spain
Basalt (scoriae)	Br 272	Savai'i, Samoa
Basalt	Br 273	Savai'i, Samoa
Basalt	Br 274	Haleakala, Hawaii, USA
Basalt	Br 275	Savai'i, Samoa
Basalt	Br 276	Savai'i, Samoa
Basalt	Br 277	Savai'i, Samoa
Basalt	Br 278	Savai'i, Samoa
Cryoconite	Br 279	Recherche Bay, Svalbard, Norway
Andesite	Br 280	Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Andesite?	Br 281	Semeru, Java, Indonesia
Schiste	Br 282	Tyren, Hammerfest, Norway
Obsidian	Br 283	Maunek? (Mausek?), near Garoet, Java, Indonesia
Basalt	Br 284	Haleakala, Hawaii, USA
Basalt?	Br 285	Dradjat, Java, Indonesia
Obsidian	Br 286	Unknown locality
Granite	Br 287	Danish Island, Svalbard, Norway
Syenite	Br 288	Märödal, Stalheim, Norway
Granite	Br 289	Amsterdam, Svalbard, Norway
Schiste	Br 290	Amsterdam, Smeerburg, Svalbard, Norway
Unidentified rock	Br 291	Recherche Bay, Svalbard, Norway
Granite	Br 292	Ile des Danois, Svalbard, Norway
Péridotite	Br 293	Recherche Bay, Svalbard, Norway
Granite	Br 294	Amsterdam Island, Svalbard, Norway

Spherite	Br 295	Green Harbour, Svalbard, Norway
Schist	Br 296	Recherche Bay, Svalbard, Norway
Granite	Br 297	Amsterdam Island, Smeerburg, Svalbard, Norway
Dacite	Br 298	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 299	Pyrgos, Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 300	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 301	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 302	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 303	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 304	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 305	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 306	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 307	Santorini, Greece
Brèche	Br308	Santorini, Greece
Dacite	Br 309	Santorini, Greece
Trachyte	Br 310	Mc Murdo Sound, Ross Sound, Sud Victoriaaland, Antarctica
Tephra	Br 311	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Ulexite	379.054	Chili
Muscovite	406.027	Auvergne, France
Tetrahedrite	406.075	Barma, Saint-Luc, Valais, Switzerland
Bismuth	406.076	Colliou de la Barma, St-Luc, Valais, Switzerland
Skutterudite	417.004	Ayer, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Nickeline	417.005	Pas de la Forcletta, Valais, Switzerland
Nickeline	417.006	Grand-Praz, Ayer, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Chalcopyrite	417.011	Ayer, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Tetrahedrite	417.012	Zinal, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Bornite	417.046	Garboulaz, Saint-Luc, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Malachite	545.019	Les Bourrimonts, Ayer, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Suisse

Collections of the Geological Museum of Lausanne (MGL)

Cylinders with synthetic pumice	11038	Unknown locality
Synthetic pumice	11038	Unknown locality
2 synthetic volcanic bombs	11039	Unknown locality
Artificial pumice	11040	Unknown locality
Marine coastal sand	14447	Koko Head, île Oahu, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA
Fumarolic salts	14448	Vesuvius, Campania, Italy
Dacitic obsidian	14449	Cabo de Gata, Andalousie, Spain

1 box of marine sand (peridot)	36471	Koko Head, île Oahu, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA
Obsidian	36472	Rakata Island, Krakatau, Java, Indonesia
Obsidian	36473	Rivière Tji Manoek, Garoet, Java, Indonesia
Realgar	36474	Papandayan, Java, Indonesia
Scoriae	w/o nr.	Chinyero, Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain

Collections of the Earth Sciences Museum in Martigny - Tissières Foundation

Azurite	t7	Gosan Mine, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Chalcocite	t15	Barma Mine, Val d'Anniviers, Valais, Switzerland
Arsenopyrite	t62	Kaltenberg Mine, Turtmann, Valais, Switzerland